

TRENDS AND THEMES IN RESEARCH ON WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS IN INDIA: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

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Abstract

In recent years, researchers have drawn greater attention to the emergence of women entrepreneurs in India, making it a major subject of study. In this study, we give a complete overview of the research environment on women entrepreneurs in India by conducting bibliometric analysis of 260 studies published between 1995 and 2022 retrieved from the Scopus database. Our research provides insight into the field's growth trends, significant authors, institutions, journals, and keywords. According to the findings, research on women entrepreneurs in India has grown significantly over the last decade, with a noteworthy increase in publications between 2019 and 2020. Agarwal and Lenka stand out among the top authors, while the Indian Institute of Technology, Roorkee tops in institutional production. Women empowerment, motivation, women's status, innovation, economic development, competencies, and challenges are among the most frequently explored topics. Furthermore, in recent years, emergent subjects such as ICT, social media, entrepreneurial satisfaction, success, risk management, and MSME have gained traction. This study highlights the existing status of research on women entrepreneurs in India and offers significant ideas for future research areas. The highlighted research gaps and suggested areas for additional exploration can assist policymakers, educators, academics, and other stakeholders in the subject of women's entrepreneurship. Overall, this study adds to our understanding of women's entrepreneurship in India, as well as its implications for economic growth.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Women entrepreneurs, Indian Entrepreneurs, Indian Women, Women Empowerment, Entrepreneurship, Bibliometric analysis, VOSviewer, Women empowerment, Indian Women.

1. INTRODUCTION

Women are a powerful force, active participants in political, professional, and managerial societies, where entrepreneurial efforts from women improves a nation's social and economic situation (Rauth & Bhardwaj, 2018). Over the past few decades, the number of women-owned enterprises has gradually increased, making a substantial contribution to global economic growth and the eradication of poverty (Sehgal & Khandelwal, 2020). While research indicates that women are participating in more innovation and entrepreneurship-related activities, there are still wide gaps to close before women and men are on an equal footing (C. Chatterjee & Ramu, 2018). Researchers identify a number of variables that contribute to the dysfunctional development of women entrepreneurs, including their business choices, a lack of good social networks, inadequate workplace flexibility, inadequate mentoring, and a lack of leadership development initiatives for women (Evans, 2011). Women are even said to have fewer business aspirations (Dhir et al., 2018; Haus et al., 2013).

While popular subjects are chosen for studying by academics and researchers, the vice versa is also true. Subjects which are deeply explored by researchers gain attention from different players of a market and contribute significantly towards its growth. More interest will be developed in women's entrepreneurship the more the topic is discussed through various media. In order to understand the themes and

trends of the sector and to help bring the topic to the attention of the general public, marketers, researchers, educators, and other important authorities, this study will examine the body of already existing literature on women entrepreneurs in India. Successful female and male entrepreneurs are studied and admired everywhere; books and articles about them are written and their approaches are imitated (Handy et al., 2007). Many literature review studies have also been conducted on the topic concerning entrepreneurship among both the genders. While few good quality reviews have already been done on the literature relating to “women entrepreneurs”, most of them target documents from all across the world. Data from individual geographical regions could present even more interesting information. As India gradually shifts its emphasis to the advancement and empowerment of women, the number of women in the workforce is increasing and few of them even go on to explore more riskier paths such as entrepreneurship, it becomes necessary to study the intellectual structure of the field in the country.

The primary objective of this study is to summarize the current state of research on Women entrepreneurship in India. The following questions help define the study's scope:

- Q1: What is the growth pattern of Women entrepreneurship in India between 1995-2022?
- Q2: Which are the most influential and highly collaborating authors, institutions, countries and journals.
- Q4: What is the distribution and trend of keywords?

The structure of this paper is as follows. Section 2 includes the methodology. Findings are presented in section 3 where sections 3.1 examines the research growth, section 3.2, section 3.3, section 3.4 examine the performance of authors, institution and journals respectively and Section 3.5 explores the prominent keyword themes. Finally, section 4 discusses the limitations and future scope and section 5 presents the conclusion.

2. METHODOLOGY

A literature review, according to Tranfield et al., (2003), carefully maps the field of research that has already been done and evaluates a potential future research direction. Bibliometric methods were developed as a result of extensive bibliographic study in the library and information sciences (Broadus, 1987; Pritchard, 1969). To be specific, bibliometric studies categorize and analyze bibliographic content by constructing representative summaries of the body of literature (Donthu et al., 2020). Researchers use bibliometric analysis for a variety of purposes, including to study the intellectual framework of an existing field and to identify developing trends in article and journal performance, collaboration patterns, and research constituents (Donthu, Kumar, Mukherjee, et al., 2021; Donthu, Kumar, Pandey, et al., 2021; Verma & Gustafsson, 2020). This study uses the SCOPUS database to acquire the data and VOSviewer for data analysis. It is noteworthy that the emergence of scientific databases like Scopus and Web of Science has made it relatively simple to acquire large volumes of bibliometric data, and bibliometric software like Gephi, Leximancer, biblioshiny, and VOSviewer allows the analysis of such data in an extremely useful manner (Donthu, Kumar, Mukherjee, et al., 2021).

A three step method was adopted to select the final dataset for the review. *First*, the keyword “women entrepreneurs” was searched on Scopus with an outcome of 2135 documents for the period 1995-2022. *Second*, certain limitations were applied to extract only the required data and eliminate others. The search was limited to only “India” under the countries category. Only “English” language documents were adopted for the final analysis based on the convenience of the authors. *Third*, the final data consisting of 260 documents was extracted in CSV form which included citation, bibliographical, abstract and indexing information from the selected documents.

The data was analyzed using VOSviewe and Scopus analyze results section where tools such as authorship, citation, co-citation and co-occurrence were utilized. Analysis section presents the growth trend of the area in the past years, a detailed map of the top contributors such as authors, institutions, countries, and sources and occurrence and co-occurrence theme of keywords.

3. ANALYSIS

This section includes an investigation of trends in the past research on women entrepreneurs in India as per various parameters, including the number of yearly publications, the performance of authors, institutions, journals, and collaboration with other countries on the basis of productivity and citation count. It also includes an analysis of the most and least popular keywords in order to determine the potential for further research in the field. Citation analysis, co-citation analysis, bibliographic coupling, and keyword co-occurrence analysis have all been used to help comprehend the area's evolutionary processes.

A total of 260 publications from 519 authors published in 156 journals were used in this research. The Scopus database contains at least one citation for 132, for a total of 1056 citations. There were 4.06 average citations per document for these articles, and there were 1.99 average authors per document. The majority of documents were published under articles (78.8%). There were notably fewer book chapters (8.8%), conference papers (6.9%), review (2.6%), notes (1.5%), books (0.76%), and editorials (0.38%). A list of the documents used in this investigation is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of documents on Women entrepreneurs in India

Items	Findings	Document type	Share	%age of Share
Total documents	260	Article	205	78.8%
Total journals	156	Book chapter	23	8.8%
Total authors	519	Conference paper	18	6.9%
Average authors	1.99	Review	7	2.6%
Cited documents	132	Note	4	1.5%
Total citations	1056	Book	2	0.76%
Average citations	4.06	Editorial	1	0.38%

3.1. Research growth

By examining the subject matter and quantity of articles published each year, it was possible to use bibliometric productivity analysis to gauge the growth of scientific literature (Povedano Montero et al., 2016). The quantity of study done on Women entrepreneurs in India did not show much growth from its inception in 1995 to 2006 with the exception of 1998 and 1999.

After 2006 they began expanding slowly with some highs and lows till 2013. After 2013 the studies on women entrepreneurs in India picked pace and the number of studies

grew exponentially. The biggest jump was witnessed from the year 2019 to 2020 with approx 31% growth in the number of publications. Surprisingly, in 2021 the growth was not as per expectations.

Only one extra article was published in 2021 compared to publications in 2020. By the end of august 2022, 34 articles were published and if it increased with the same rate throughout the year, around 51 articles could be expected which would amount for around 30- 31 % of yearly growth. The evolution of the number of publications in the field of women entrepreneurs in India from 1995 to 2022 is depicted in Fig. 1. To comprehend the average growth rate of the publishings in the region, a trendline has also been created.

Fig 1: Total number of publications per year and trendline of the documents

The top 30 documents, as determined by the amount of citations they have received, are shown in Table 2. The top 3 papers with the highest citation count were (Agarwal & Lenka, 2015), (Rauth Bhardwaj, 2014)), and (V.Mathew & Natarajan, 2011)), with 70 (6.6%), 49 (4.6%), and 48 (4.5%) citations respectively. To determine the articles that performed well on a yearly average, the top 30 publications' total citations per year (TCpY) were calculated.

Due to the fact that the articles were published in various years, this provides a more accurate foundation for evaluating their effectiveness. The top three documents with the highest average citations were (V.Mathew & Natarajan, 2011), (Khandelwal & Sehgal, 2018), and (Agarwal et al., 2020) with yearly averages of 48, 22, and 15.5 respectively.

Table 2: Details of the top 30 documents on Women entrepreneurs in India

Ranking	Author and year	Title	Source	DOI	TC	TCpY
1	(Agarwal & Lenka, 2015)	Study on work-life balance of women entrepreneurs – review and research agenda	Industrial and Commercial Training	10.1108/ICT-01-2015-0006	70	10
2	(Rauth Bhardwaj, 2014)	Impact of education and training on performance of women entrepreneurs: A	Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging	10.1108/JEE-E-05-2013-0014	49	4.45

		study in emerging market context	Economies			
3	(V.Mathew & Natarajan, 2011)	An exploratory study on the work-life balance of women entrepreneurs in South India	Asian Academy of Management Journal	ISSN 19858280	48	48
4	(Raghuvanshi et al., 2017)	Analysis of Barriers to Women Entrepreneurship: The DEMATEL Approach	Journal of Entrepreneurship	10.1177/0971355717708848	47	9.4
5	(Prasad et al., 2013)	Women entrepreneurs and business venture growth: an examination of the influence of human and social capital resources in an Indian context	Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship	10.1080/08276331.2013.821758	42	3.5
6	(Williams & Gurtoo, 2011a)	Evaluating women entrepreneurs in the informal sector: Some evidence from India	Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship	10.1142/S1084946711001914	40	2.85
7	(Williams & Gurtoo, 2011b)	Women entrepreneurs in the Indian informal sector: Marginalisation dynamics or institutional rational choice?	International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship	10.1108/17566261111114953	40	2.85
8	(Agarwal & Lenka, 2018)	Why research is needed in women entrepreneurship in India: a viewpoint	International Journal of Social Economics	10.1108/IJS E-07-2017-0298	33	8.25
9	(Agarwal & Lenka, 2016)	An exploratory study on the development of women entrepreneurs: Indian cases	Journal of Research in Marketing and Entrepreneurship	10.1108/JRME-04-2015-0024	32	3.5
10	(Agarwal et al., 2020)	A qualitative approach towards crucial factors for sustainable development of women social entrepreneurship: Indian cases	Journal of Cleaner Production	10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123135	31	15.5
11	(Lenka & Agarwal, 2017)	Role of women entrepreneurs and NGOs in promoting entrepreneurship: case studies from Uttarakhand, India	Journal of Asia Business Studies	10.1108/JABS-07-2015-0088	26	5.2
12	(Khandelwal & Sehgal, 2018)	Exploring work-family interface for Indian women entrepreneurs	Gender in Management	10.1108/GM-04-2016-0075	22	22
13	(Vijaya & Kamalanabhan, 1998)	A scale to assess entrepreneurial motivation	Journal of Entrepreneurship	10.1177/097135579800700204	21	0.87
14	(Handy et al., 2007)	To profit or not to profit: Women entrepreneurs in India	Nonprofit Management and Leadership	10.1002/nml.159	20	1.3
15	(Nair, 2020)	The link between women entrepreneurship, innovation and stakeholder engagement: A review	Journal of Business Research	10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.06.038	19	9.5
16	(Agarwal & Lenka, 2017)	Does growth of ventures depend on competencies?: Selected cases from India	International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business	10.1504/IJESB.2017.084089	19	3.8
17	(Shastri et al., 2019)	Motivations and challenges of women entrepreneurs: Experiences of small businesses in Jaipur city of Rajasthan	International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy	10.1108/IJSSP-09-2018-0146	18	6
18	(N. Chatterjee et	A structural model assessing key factors affecting women's	Journal of Entrepreneurship	10.1108/JEE E-08-2016-	18	6

	al., 2019)	entrepreneurial success: Evidence from India	in Emerging Economies	0030		
19	(Jha et al., 2018)	Performance-oriented factors for women entrepreneurs – a scale development perspective	Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies	10.1108/JEE-E-08-2017-0053	18	4.5
20	(Arul Paramanandam & Packirisamy, 2015)	An empirical study on the impact of micro enterprises on women empowerment	Journal of Enterprising Communities	10.1108/JEC-08-2014-0017	17	2.4

3.2. Most productive authors

The number of authors who publish in a certain field reflects how well-known and significant the field of study is. The authors with the most publications and citations are considered top authors.

The top authors in a field should be examined in order to understand their methodology and learn from them. A total of 519 authors published literature on women entrepreneurs in India. Table 3 includes the top 10 authors in the field based on the quantity of documents and the number of citations.

Agarwal, S, and Lenka, U. were the top authors with the most amount of work as well as citation count. Other authors such as Agrawal, V, Banu, J., and Baral, R. were some of the authors with a high quantity of publications. Whereas, Gurtoo a., Williams c.c., and Agrawal v. were some of the authors with high number of citations.

In order to have a more valid parameter to figure out the top authors, the average citations per paper were also calculated for the top authors and it represents a totally different picture. According to average citations, Rauth bhardwaj b., Mathew r.v., Agrawal r. and Rauth bhardwaj b. Were among the top authors.

Table 3: Top 10 authors on the basis of total publications and citations

Ranking	Authors	No. of Papers	TC	TC/paper	Ranking	Authors	TC	No. of papers	TC/paper
1	Agarwal, S.	10	239	23.9		Agarwal s.	239	10	23.9
2	Lenka, U.	7	211	30.14		Lenka u.	211	7	30.14
3	Agrawal, V.	5	59	11.8		Gurtoo a.	80	2	40
4	Banu, J.	4	3	0.75		Williams c.c.	80	2	40
5	Baral, R.	4	3	0.75		Agrawal v.	59	5	11.8
6	Velmurugan, R.	4	6	1.5		Panchanatham n.	51	2	25.5
7	Jan, S.	3	8	2.67		Rauth bhardwaj b.	49	1	49
8	Kamalanabhan, T.J.	3	25	8.3		Mathew r.v.	48	1	48
9	Nair, S.R.	3	27	9		Agrawal r.	47	1	47
10	Sathiyabama, P.	3	4	1.3		Ghosh p.k.	47	1	47

3.3. Institution-wise analysis

160 different institutions from all over India participated in the articles that were published in the field. Indian Institute of Technology, The Indian Roorkee, Indian Institute of Technology, Madras and GLA University, Mathura were some of the top contributing institutions contributing to the research on Women entrepreneurship in India. Top 10 universities with the most publications are mentioned in table 4. The

table lists the total number of publications, total number of citations, and average number of citations per document for the top 10 universities. IIT Roorkee and GLA University in Mathura appear to have the most citations among the top universities. However, while publishing a sizable volume of research, institutions like IIT, Madras, Symbiosis International Deemed University, SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, Amity University, and others do not have a high citation ratio.

Table 4: Top 10 institutions on the basis of total publications and citations

Ranking	Institutions	No. of Papers	TC	TC/ paper
1	Indian Institute of Technology, Roorkee	10	261	26.1
2	Indian Institute of Technology, Madras	8	30	3.75
3	GLA University, Mathura	8	85	10.6
4	Symbiosis International Deemed University	7	10	1.4
5	Birla Institute of Technology and Science, Pilani	6	30	5
6	SRM Institute of Science and Technology	5	2	0.4
7	Sathyabama Institute of Science and Technology	5	20	4
8	Indian Institute of Technology, Delhi	5	5	1
9	Amity University	5	0	0
10	Karpagam Academy of Higher Education	5	8	1.6

Fig 2: Yearly productivity of top 10 Institutions

Figure 2 displays a timeline chart of publications by the top 10 universities. It indicates that even though the Indian Institute of Technology, Madras had published its first article in 1998, it did not publish the second one until 2008. With exception of 2008 and 2009, the top authors only began to publish regularly starting in 2013.

The same pattern is also consistent in the overall research growth in the area as found in the 'research growth' section of this article which concludes that the amount of research relating to women entrepreneurship in India started to pick pace from 2013

onwards. This may be due to growing awareness of women's empowerment and the value of women in the workplace over the past 10 to 15 years.

The graph also offers hope for increasing future research on women entrepreneurs from renowned universities, which is urgently needed for a better societal representation of women in India and across countries.

3.4. Top source journals

This section provides a summary of the sources and journals that have contributed most to the development of the area. The dataset contained articles from 156 journals, with an average of 1.6 papers and 6.76 citations per journal. A journal is a regular publication that comes out on a regular basis (monthly, yearly, etc.) with the goal of advancing and monitoring the progress of the field it represents (Muhuri et al., 2019).

Table 5 lists the top 10 journals based on the volume of papers, citations and citations per paper. The top three journals with the most publications in the field were International Journal Of Advanced Science And Technology, Journal Of Enterprising Communities, and Vision.

Among the others listed in the table, the journals with the largest number of citations were Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies, Journal of Entrepreneurship, and Industrial and Commercial Training.

Average citations per paper were also calculated in order to present an even more reliable measure of identifying the top journals with quality content. Asian academy of management journal had the highest average citations followed by Journal of developmental entrepreneurship and Industrial and commercial training.

Table 5: Top productive journals VS Top cited journals

Ranking	Journals	No. of Papers	TC	TC/paper	Ranking	Journals	TC	No. of papers	TC/paper
1	Journal Of Enterprising Communities	8	60	7.5	1	Journal of entrepreneurship in emerging economies	94	5	18.8
2	International Journal Of Advanced Science And Technology	7	4	0.57	2	Journal of entrepreneurship	73	4	18.25
3	Vision	7	13	1.85	3	Industrial and commercial training	71	2	35.5
4	Prabandhan Indian Journal Of Management	6	4	0.66	4	Journal of enterprising communities	60	8	7.5
5	Emerald Emerging Markets Case Studies	5	0	0	5	Asian academy of management journal	48	1	48
6	International Journal Of Applied Business And Economic	5	1	0.2	6	International journal of gender and entrepreneurship	47	4	11.75

	Research								
7	International Journal Of Entrepreneurship And Small Business	<u>5</u>	35	7	7	Journal of small business and entrepreneurship	46	3	15.33
8	International Journal Of Mechanical Engineering And Technology	<u>5</u>	8	1.6	8	Journal of developmental entrepreneurship	40	1	40
9	Journal Of Entrepreneurship In Emerging Economies	<u>5</u>	94	18.8	9	Gender in management	38	2	19
10	International Journal Of Gender And Entrepreneurship	<u>4</u>	47	11.75	10	International journal of social economics	36	2	18

Yearly output by top publishing journals

Fig 3: Yearly output by top publishing journals

Fig 3 suggests that the top 10 journals with the highest publications started publishing in 2011. The volume of documents did not significantly increase until 2017. The journals didn't publish more than two papers on a yearly average until 2017. The top journals' collective output appears to be increasing as of 2018.

3.5. Prominent subject areas

Most papers related to women empowerment in India were published in the subject area of Business, Management and Accounting (32.8%) followed by Economics, Econometrics (18.1%) and Finance and Social Sciences (13.3%). Agricultural and Biological Sciences, Environmental Science, Nursing and Arts and Humanities were some of the subject areas where women entrepreneurship related research was not as prominent as in other areas. As about one in three of the growth-oriented entrepreneurs operating globally today are women (Research Shows Women Entrepreneurs Are Key to Inclusive Economic Growth), research related to women entrepreneurs across disciplines should be encouraged.

Fig 4 shows the percentage of contribution by each subject area in the overall research on women empowerment in India.

Fig 4: Documents by Subject area

3.6. Country-wise analysis

Research collaboration is an important factor in promoting quality work. As the world is progressing towards becoming a global village, collaborations between researchers from different countries and territories are also improving. About 18 other countries have collaborated with Indian authors in the dataset considered in this article. Fig. 5 displays a network map of these collaborations between India and other countries. The frequency of collaboration is represented by the size of the circles. The United States (9 papers), the United Kingdom (5 papers), Canada (4 papers), and Malaysia (4 papers) had the highest amount of collaboration with India.

Table 6: Top collaborating countries

Countries that have collaborated with India	No. of documents	No. of citations
United States	9	94
United Kingdom	5	90
Canada	4	27
Malaysia	4	4
Australia	3	11
Italy	2	0
Bahrain	1	6
Bangladesh	1	2
Ethiopia	1	3
France	1	6
Iraq	1	0
Kuwait	1	5
Netherlands	1	0
Nigeria	1	0
North Macedonia	1	7
Saudi Arabia	1	0
Thailand	1	16
The United Arab Emirates	1	20

Fig 5: Network map of country collaborations

3.7. Research Keyword Analysis

Fig 6: Most frequent keywords

For the study in this section, 61 keywords with a minimum of 3 occurrences were taken into consideration. The top five keywords with the highest frequency were women empowerment (14), empowerment (12), motivation (12), women's status (9), and innovation (8). The network of co-occurring keywords is displayed through a network map that shows the linkage and density of keywords (Fig. 7) in order to further simplify the examination of the co-occurrence of keywords. The Red cluster, Blue cluster, Green cluster, Purple cluster, and other associated clusters appear to dominate the subject on the network map. A list of keywords from different clusters is shown in Fig 8, along with the frequency that they occur.

Fig 7: Network map of co-occurring keywords

Fig 8: Major keyword clusters

A timeline of keyword occurrences was prepared using the overlay visualization from VosViewer to indicate the years in which they were most popular (Fig 9). The year 2016 indicated a popularity of studies from Karnataka. Studies relating to culture, marketing and Economic development seem to be the epicenter of the year. Towards 2017, keywords such as Women empowerment, economic growth, sustainability, micro enterprises and small scale industries dominated the research field. 2018 and 2019 were popular for research relating to motivation, success, competencies, social media, etc and 2020 onwards subjects like innovation, entrepreneurial satisfaction, start- ups, electronic commerce, challenges and risk management were preferred to be studied in connection with women A literature review, according to Tranfield, Denyer, and Smart (2003), carefully maps the field of research that has already been done and evaluates a potential future research direction.

Fig 9: Keyword Occurrence Timeline

Certain keywords that did not have enough occurrences such as technology adoption, ICT, women's employment, self-efficacy, social media, success, risk management, etc., could be studied in future studies to explore different dimension of the Women empowerment domain in India.

4. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE SCOPE

Despite the extensive bibliometric analysis performed in this study, some limitations must be addressed. Firstly, the analysis is limited to Scopus-indexed research papers. Other relevant studies published in non-indexed or regional journals may have been overlooked, potentially leading to a bias in the results. Future study might consider using a larger range of databases and sources to ensure a more comprehensive coverage of the literature on women entrepreneurs in India.

Second, the study's emphasis on bibliometric analysis limits the investigation to quantitative metrics such as publication and citation counts, while ignoring the qualitative components of the research. Incorporating a content analysis methodology

could provide a more in-depth understanding of the topics, procedures, and theoretical frameworks used in the literature, expanding the insights gained from this research.

Several avenues for future investigation appear from this study's findings. To begin, conducting a systematic review or meta-analysis of the literature can provide a more in-depth synthesis of the important findings and aid in the development of sound conclusions on the state of women entrepreneurship research in India.

Second, researching cultural, geographical, and socioeconomic differences within India can provide a more comprehensive picture of women's entrepreneurship experiences and problems. A comparative study across different states or regions could identify unique elements influencing women's entrepreneurship engagement and inspire focused policy actions.

Furthermore, investigating the intersectionality of women's entrepreneurship, such as the impact of caste, religion, or urban-rural divisions, could reveal new aspects of analysis and provide insights into the different experiences.

Longitudinal studies that track the evolution of women entrepreneurs in India through time could also provide insights into changing trends, issues, and progress. Policymakers and researchers alike might benefit from understanding how various government efforts and economic changes affect women's entrepreneurial endeavors.

Finally, qualitative research that digs into the lived experiences, motivations, and goals of women entrepreneurs in India can provide a more complete picture of their journeys, decision-making processes, and support systems. Scholars may contribute more extensively to the advancement of knowledge on women entrepreneurship in India and build an environment conducive to women's empowerment and economic progress by resolving these constraints and pursuing the suggested future study areas.

5. CONCLUSION

The paper presents an analysis of trends in research on women entrepreneurs published between 1995 and 2022. The dataset was restricted to just one country, namely India. The last ten years have seen the publication of almost 90% of all the literature in this area. There were 519 authors and 260 articles for a total of 1056 citations. 156 journals and 160 institutions participated in studies on women's entrepreneurship in India as of the date the data for this paper was obtained. With the exception of 1998 and 1999, the volume of research on women entrepreneurs in India has not grown much from its beginning in 1995 to 2006. After 2006, they began to slowly expand, experiencing several peaks and troughs until 2013. The pace and volume of studies increased dramatically after 2013. The biggest spike in publications was seen between the years 2019 and 2020 with a 31% surge. Agarwal, S. published the highest number of research papers and Jan, S., and Kamalanabhan, T.J. had the highest average citations per document. The top university with the most publications and citations was Indian Institute of Technology, Roorkee. Journal Of Enterprising Communities, International Journal Of Advanced Science And Technology, Journal of entrepreneurship in emerging economies and Journal of entrepreneurship were among the top journals. Certain keywords such as women empowerment, empowerment, motivation, women's status, Innovation, economic development, competencies and challenges have been studied in depth whereas others such as

ICT, social media, entrepreneurial satisfaction success, risk management, MSME need more attention.

The bibliometric investigation of research on women's empowerment in India will be helpful to academics and professionals in a variety of ways. They will learn more about the background, growth, and present developments of the field. Academics will be able to determine which topics still need further study. In the big picture, it will help in some way to raise awareness about the participation of women in the entrepreneurial sector of a country where women have started to slowly but surely take control of their rights and their potential.

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References

- 1) Agarwal, S., & Lenka, U. (2015). Study on work-life balance of women entrepreneurs – review and research agenda. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 47(7), 356–362. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ICT-01-2015-0006>
- 2) Agarwal, S., & Lenka, U. (2016). An exploratory study on the development of women entrepreneurs: Indian cases. *Journal of Research in Marketing and Entrepreneurship*, 18(2), 232–247. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JRME-04-2015-0024>
- 3) Agarwal, S., & Lenka, U. (2017). Does growth of ventures depend on competencies?: Selected cases from India. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 31, 227. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJESB.2017.10004850>
- 4) Agarwal, S., & Lenka, U. (2018). Why research is needed in women entrepreneurship in India: A viewpoint. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 45(7), 1042–1057. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSE-07-2017-0298>
- 5) Agarwal, S., Lenka, U., Singh, K., Agrawal, V., & Agrawal, A. M. (2020). A qualitative approach towards crucial factors for sustainable development of women social entrepreneurship: Indian cases. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 274, 123135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123135>
- 6) Arul Paramanandam, D., & Packirisamy, P. (2015). An empirical study on the impact of micro enterprises on women empowerment. *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*, 9(4), 298–314. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEC-08-2014-0017>
- 7) Broadus, R. N. (1987). Toward a definition of “bibliometrics.” *Scientometrics*, 12(5), 373–379. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02016680>
- 8) Chatterjee, C., & Ramu, S. (2018). Gender and its rising role in modern Indian innovation and entrepreneurship. *IIMB Management Review*, 30(1), 62–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iimb.2017.11.006>
- 9) Chatterjee, N., Das, N., & Srivastava, N. K. (2019). A structural model assessing key factors affecting women's entrepreneurial success: Evidence from India. *Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies*, 11(1), 122–151. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEEE-08-2016-0030>
- 10) Dhir, S., Dhir, S., & Samanta, P. (2018). Defining and developing a scale to measure strategic thinking. *Foresight*, 20. <https://doi.org/10.1108/FS-10-2017-0059>
- 11) Donthu, N., Kumar, S., Mukherjee, D., Pandey, N., & Lim, W. M. (2021). How to conduct a bibliometric analysis: An overview and guidelines. *Journal of Business Research*, 133, 285–296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.04.070>

- 12) Donthu, N., Kumar, S., Pandey, N., & Gupta, P. (2021). Forty years of the International Journal of Information Management: A bibliometric analysis. *International Journal of Information Management*, 57, 102307. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2020.102307>
- 13) Donthu, N., Kumar, S., & Pattnaik, D. (2020). Forty-five years of Journal of Business Research: A bibliometric analysis. *Journal of Business Research*, 109, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.10.039>
- 14) Evans, D. (2011). Room at the top: Advancement and equity for women in the business world. *National Civic Review*, 100. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ncr.20061>
- 15) Handy, F., Ranade, B., & Kassam, M. (2007). To profit or not to profit: Women entrepreneurs in India. *Nonprofit Management and Leadership*, 17(4), 383–401. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nml.159>
- 16) Haus, I., Steinmetz, H., Isidor, R., & Kabst, R. (2013). Gender effects on entrepreneurial intention: A meta-analytical structural equation model. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 5(2), 130.
- 17) Jha, P., Makkad, M., & Mittal, S. (2018). Performance-oriented factors for women entrepreneurs – a scale development perspective. *Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies*, 10(2), 329–360. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEEE-08-2017-0053>
- 18) Khandelwal, P., & Sehgal, A. (2018). Exploring work-family interface for Indian women entrepreneurs. *Gender in Management: An International Journal*, 33(3), 203–216. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GM-04-2016-0075>
- 19) Lenka, U., & Agarwal, S. (2017). Role of women entrepreneurs and NGOs in promoting entrepreneurship: Case studies from Uttarakhand, India. *Journal of Asia Business Studies*, 11(4), 451–465. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JABS-07-2015-0088>
- 20) Nair, S. R. (2020). The link between women entrepreneurship, innovation and stakeholder engagement: A review. *Journal of Business Research*, 119, 283–290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.06.038>
- 21) Prasad, V. K., Naidu, G. M., Kinnera Murthy, B., Winkel, D. E., & Ehrhardt, K. (2013). Women entrepreneurs and business venture growth: An examination of the influence of human and social capital resources in an Indian context. *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*, 26(4), 341–364. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08276331.2013.821758>
- 22) Pritchard, A. (1969). Statistical Bibliography or Bibliometrics? *Journal of Documentation*, 25, 348–349.
- 23) Raghuvanshi, J., Agrawal, R., & Ghosh, P. K. (2017). Analysis of Barriers to Women Entrepreneurship: The DEMATEL Approach. *The Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 26(2), 220–238. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0971355717708848>
- 24) Rauth, B., & Bhardwaj, B. (2018). Can education empower women through entrepreneurial marketing: A model for upliftment of community services. *Journal of Enterprising Communities People and Places in the Global Economy*, 12, 19–31. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEC-01-2017-0004>
- 25) Rauth Bhardwaj, B. (2014). Impact of education and training on performance of women entrepreneurs: A study in emerging market context. *Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies*, 6(1), 38–52. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEEE-05-2013-0014>
- 26) Sehgal, A., & Khandelwal, P. (2020). Work–family interface of women entrepreneurs: Evidence from India. *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*, 9(3), 411–428. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SAJBS-11-2019-0213>
- 27) Shastri, S., Shastri, S., & Pareek, A. (2019). Motivations and challenges of women entrepreneurs: Experiences of small businesses in Jaipur city of Rajasthan. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, 39(5/6), 338–355. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSSP-09-2018-0146>
- 28) Tranfield, D., Denyer, D., & Smart, P. (2003). Towards a Methodology for Developing Evidence-Informed Management Knowledge by Means of Systematic Review. *British Journal of Management*, 14(3), 207–222. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8551.00375>

- 29) Verma, S., & Gustafsson, A. (2020). Investigating the emerging COVID-19 research trends in the field of business and management: A bibliometric analysis approach. *Journal of Business Research*, 118, 253–261. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.06.057>
- 30) Vijaya, V., & Kamalanabhan, T. J. (1998). A Scale to Assess Entrepreneurial Motivation. *The Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 7(2), 183–198. <https://doi.org/10.1177/097135579800700204>
- 31) V.Mathew, R., & Natarajan, P. (2011). An exploratory study on the work-life balance of women entrepreneurs in South India. *Asian Academy of Management Journal*, 16.
- 32) Williams, C. C., & Gurtoo, A. (2011a). Evaluating Women Entrepreneurs In The Informal Sector: Some Evidence From India. *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship*, 16(03), 351–369. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S1084946711001914>
- 33) Williams, C. C., & Gurtoo, A. (2011b). Women entrepreneurs in the Indian informal sector: Marginalisation dynamics or institutional rational choice? *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 3(1), 6–22. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17566261111114953>